

What are the attitudes of local stakeholders towards multi-functional changes in woodlands of the Ukrainian Carpathians?

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In this research stakeholder attitudes towards ecosystem-based forest strategies and management practices in marginalized mountain areas of the Ukrainian Carpathians were analysed. The focus was on multi-functional changes in upland woodlands, as those were viewed by relevant stakeholders. A final goal was to assist decision-makers in evaluation (e.g. through stakeholder evaluation using the suggested method) and implementation (through stakeholder engagement) of sustainable forest policy and management decisions. The Q-method, with the sequential application of its correlation and factor analytical tools, was applied to elucidate a range of existing attitudes (e.g. towards the expansion of woodlands under climate change and other drivers) and the spectrum of sustainability (its ecological, economic and social components) to which they relate. Dominant attitudes of representatives of relevant stakeholder groups towards multi-functional changes in forestry in the Carpathian Mountains were revealed and explained, along with key factors influencing the attitudinal diversity. The results improve our understanding of stakeholder priorities and of commonalities and differences in existing attitudes/perceptions, providing some indication of how the diversity of attitudes towards forestry changes (e.g. integration of woodlands in mountain landscapes) could potentially influence sustainable forestry decisions, including those promoting participation and enhancing social innovation. At times, entirely opposite attitudes (e.g. of the so-called Conservationists and Productivists attitudinal groups) towards forestry practices and key objectives of forestry in the Carpathian uplands were revealed. However, it was found out that overall people put strong emphasis on multi-functional forestry and stakeholder engagement in decision making processes.

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